

1 **MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT MODEL**

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3 Organizational innovation and scaling of Waste-To-Energy plants for

4 recyclable material collectors' associations in the city of Uberlandia -MG

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1 ABSTRACT

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3 In order to mitigate environmental impacts of trash generation and to build up
4 alternatives for work and revenue, this paper has investigated the dimensioning of a syngas
5 generation plant from municipal solid waste (MSW) for collectors associations and came to its
6 conclusions by research on the literature.

7 The legal applicability and the partnerships for organizational residue innovation in
8 management were analyzed in the perspective of a public utility system. The reactor model was
9 designed after extensive research on the available technologies to achieve the lowest price in
10 the implementation of the system and to grant scalability. It was verified that the direct
11 utilization of fuel produced by two-stage pyrolysis of MSW is a very promising resolution of
12 economic and socioenvironmental issues of the constant rising in the volume of trash generated
13 in the cities.

14
15 **Key-words:** Organizational innovation; Waste To Energy, Circular economy, Pyrolysis.

17 1. INTRODUCTION

18
19 According to data from the World Bank, it is estimated that by 2050 almost 70% more
20 waste will be generated around the world than in 2020. To minimize this impact, some countries
21 seek to use technology and innovation, with energy recovery, mainly pyrolysis, as priority in
22 management (ANDRADE, 2022; IPEA, 2021; ENGELMANN, 2021; FREITAS, 2021;
23 TULIO, 2020).

24 In Brazil, the National Solid Waste Policy (PNRS), established by Law No.
25 12,305/2010, determines that the public sector, in all its spheres, and the private sector carry
26 out solid waste management. To relate universities to this development, there are legal

1 mechanisms for regulating technological extension (Law No. 10,973/04; Law No. 13,243/16)
2 and research and extension practices at universities. These laws of technological innovation
3 enables the social organization of production through partnerships, using the model of Silveira
4 (2010). The model's call for strategic alliances relates the National Biofuels Policy - RenovaBio
5 (13,576/17) and organizations in coordinated cooperation for the circular economy, a
6 structuring factor for the local productive arrangement (LPA) of a popular solidarity economy
7 for the biomass market niche energy (BETANHO; FERNANTES, 2017).

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9 **2. GOALS**

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11 Dimensioning thermochemical and organizational processes to enable the conversion of
12 urban solid waste into fuels and fertilizers, offering opportunities to generate work and income
13 through the circular economy and organizational models in the MSW recycling process,
14 supported by normative legislation and technical literature.

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16 **3. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

17 **3.1. Methodology**

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19 In the documentary research on public policies, Law No. 12,305/2010 (National Solid
20 Waste Policy), Law No. 13,019/2014 (Regulatory framework for the third sector), Law No.
21 13,243/2016 (Institutional Legal Framework –on effective extension) were analyzed. Law No.
22 13,576/2017 (National Biofuel Policy - RenovaBio), Law No. 8,080/1990 (SUS Health
23 Determinants – on sustainability) and Law No. 8,142/1990 (Provides for the conditions for the
24 promotion, protection and recovery of health, the organization and operation of the

1 corresponding services and other measures), in addition to the use of data from the Institute of
2 Geography and Statistics (IBGE).

3 Legal tools, such as PNRS (Fontão, 2020) and MROSC (in a device that triggers what
4 was passed over by Soares (2019) on transparency and guarantees for CSOs), indicate social
5 technology instruments for methodological coordination of “strategic alliances” in involvement
6 of intersectoral social partnerships, a participatory management model in order to guarantee
7 public appropriation, knowledge of productive environments in connected circuits of people
8 and technologies in sustainability processes, and thus, the management of MSW in an
9 organizational form in order to ensure rights for individual and collective actors who trigger
10 innovations, inventions, patents and productive activities of a popular solidarity economy
11 (SILVEIRA., 2010).

12 The methodology used to characterize urban solid waste (MSW) and domestic solid
13 waste (RDO) was extracted from experiments carried out with biomass of animal and vegetable
14 origin, with simulations and thermal analysis prepared by De Lima (2021), in order to apply
15 new technologies to use this raw material. Using thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) and
16 differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), the efficiency of the biomass transition into waste
17 natural gas was verified.

19 **3.2. Thermochemical treatment of MSW in circulating fluidized bed (CFB)**

20
21 CFB reactors were researched with the aim of optimizing the conversion of waste into
22 energy in an efficient and sustainable way. In a pyrolysis reactor, two stages occur: the primary,
23 where the biomass decomposes into solid coal, bio-oil , gas and water, and the secondary, where
24 additional decomposition occurs and the formation of more gaseous products. A longer

1 residence time and temperature increase will produce more synthesis gases (BITTENCOURT,
2 FP, 2020).

3 The design of the pyrolysis reactor takes into account its operating conditions, local
4 MSW supply, associations available space and presence of local demand for the subproducts.
5 The final product energetic value depends on the PCI ratio of biomass inputs (MJ/kg). Its
6 efficiency in terms of yield is controlled by residence time, biomass supply rate and heat transfer
7 (NAGARAJA, 2021).

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9 **4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS**

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11 **4.1. Quantitative sizing of MSW waste**

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13 According to the current municipal MSW treatment model (DMAE, 2021), there is a
14 total of 166.76 tons daily of MSW reject in recyclable materials collectors' associations and
15 landfills in Uberlândia, whose use on thermochemical treatment is evaluated by the present
16 study. This quantity makes it possible, using data from Scarafiz (2023), to implement a
17 gasification plant with 0% IRR and free of interest as a public investment with the purpose of
18 managing 150 tons/day of RDF in an environmentally and socially responsible manner. through
19 the energy transition from waste to renewable energy and income generation (MORANDEIRA-
20 ARCA et al., 2021). The direct utilization of fuel generated by two-stage pyrolysis and the nature
21 of CFB reactors makes the system scalable for smaller and bigger cities.

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4.2. Municipal MSW management model

The transition from biomass from MSW/RDO to renewable energy has bases in the PNRS regarding sustainable development (requiring adequate logistical infrastructure to support trade in biomass raw materials and intermediaries) and is accompanied by interrelated environmental, social and economic concerns (MURADIN et al, 2020; MENEZES, 2019).

Figure 1: Circular economy model in MSW treatment management

Source: Marani I. and Silveira H. (2023);

Figure 1 refers to the circular economy model for MSW management, through strategic partnerships (liabilities below, assets above). It is based on innovation at two levels: the individual level and the collective level of the municipal solids management plan. Each of the agents involved benefits in exchange for their cooperation. Using technologies at their individual level, they are able to increase their income, generate training, receive benefits such as tax incentives and meet the objectives of national public policies and international agreements for sustainable development such as the sustainable development goals (UN, 2000). When at the collective level of the municipal waste management plan, they generate jobs and cooperate for sustainable development through infrastructure, strategic alliances and shared management of MSW treatment.

4.3. Prior treatment in partners

Considering the water content required in the system and the data used from Carneiro (2007) and Shafiq et al. (2021), it is demonstrated that it is unnecessary to subject the waste to drying treatment, saving 93.24MW (R\$29,325.00 to R\$43,089.00 per month between off-peak and peak times, respectively, and also saves with the taxes were exempted from CSO associative activities, through modeling for filling gas cylinders, eliminating the need for storage equipment that makes the process more expensive, in addition to reducing the space required.

The crusher used as an example has dimensions of 1800 x 800 x 1150 mm and weighs 205 kg, with the capacity to crush up to 1.24 tons/hour of MSW each. It is estimated that the base cost passed on to associations by partners per ton of RDF delivered varies between R\$23.01 and R\$26.44. Freight costs were not accounted for, and it is necessary to ensure that this fee passed on to associations can fluctuate.

Figure 2: Association Partners in the Management Model

Source: The author (2023)

1 71.6% of this waste is in controlled landfills, which demonstrates their importance as
2 active agents and main partners of associations in the proposed waste management model.

4.4. Equipment in associations:

FIGURE 3: Blueprint model for waste picker associations.

Source: Marani I. and Silveira H. (2023);

6
7 Figure 3 illustrates the space of the RDF transformation plant into cooking gas and
8 biochar in recyclable collectors' associations. 3.4ton. of RDF are processed per hour in each
9 plant. It is estimated that a biochar storage space of up to 30m² is needed for sale by associations.
10 For the bottling plant, the turnover every hour is 248 cylinders.

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1 4.4.1. CFB Reactor

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3 For the kinetic model and for the sizing of the CFB, a static model is assumed, as in
4 Trendewicz et al. (2014). Given the speed of fluidization, fast pyrolysis requires the reaction
5 to occur within 2 to 2.5 s. Particles with a diameter above 200 μm take 0.38 seconds to heat
6 their core to the point of pyrolysis, compromising the ideal condition for the fast pyrolysis
7 model (VELDEN et al., 2010).

8 The reactor model used applies adaptations to the pyrolysis process for gasification of
9 RDF bio pyrolysis oil, seeking to increase efficiency in biofuel production using steam
10 reforming of hydrocarbons, fluidization gas rich in CO_2 , thermal breakdown of tar, and other
11 adaptations from Manon Van der Velden 's circulating fluidized bed reactor model . A similar
12 experimental study is by Alamsyah et al. (2014), which already brings the production of
13 synthesis gas for cooking or heating, from the gasification of biomass pellets.

14 convection heat transfer coefficient in a CFB is estimated at 620 W/m.K from the results
15 of Kobro and Brereton (1986), thus finding 9537.93 kW . Since not only external convection
16 but also internal conduction is important, the overall picture is expressed by the Biot number :

17 Van De Velden, M. et al. (2010) estimates that a 200 μm particle ($r = 100 \mu\text{m}$) at 773
18 K has $\text{Bi} = 0.83$ for a $h = 1250/\text{cm.k}$.

19 According to Rodrigues CJC et al (2023) Marcelino, Nogueira and Lora (2003), the PCI
20 of the gas produced by the biomass fraction is 5.1716 MJ/kg , while its enthalpy is 3.18 MJ/kg .
21 The negative value is due to the enthalpy of formation of elements in the gas composition. The
22 enthalpy of formation for biomass and fluidization gases is 8 MJ/kg .

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Figure 4: CFB Reactor Model for Synthesis Gas Production by Associations – OSCs

Source: Marani I. and Silveira H. (2023)

1 In most biomass species, the reaction rate constant is $>0.5/s$, corresponding to a fast
 2 reaction. The endothermic heat enthalpy (h) of the reaction varies from 207 to 434 kJ.kg⁻¹
 3 (PCIaverage = 0.3205 MJ/kg). The results match those in the literature. The MSW species
 4 analyzed have an average of 20.25 MJ/kg, higher than the PCI of the plant biomass used in the
 5 CFB by VELDEN et al. (2007), 19.40MJ/kg. According to the literature, increasing the
 6 percentage of plastic and tire waste increases the PCI in the CFB.

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Figure 5: Mass Flow of the municipal plan for MSW management.

Source: Marani I. and Silveira H. (2023);

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The process heat is entirely supplied by burning gas in the combustion chamber, which indirectly heats the material in the circulating bed. The fluidization gas is composed of pyrolysis gas, exhaust gases and water vapor.

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4.4.2. GAS CYLINDER PACKAGING

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Based on the study by Neto et al. (2021), we sought to estimate the fixed costs of maintaining a cooking gas bottling and distribution plant.

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Considering the flow in the riser and the total of two risers in the model, a maximum of up to 498 P13 containers per hour of production is expected, requiring a total of 17 filling nozzles in both plants for the system to work at maximum capacity. A total cost of R\$233,400 per month is expected for bottling the synthesis gas. The expected benefit of the project is the monthly production of 221,538 cylinders of gas by two associations, together processing 6.8 tons/h of RDF.

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1 5. CONCLUSIONS

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3 According to the literature, reusing the organic fractions of MSW for cooking gas and
4 biochar is feasible. With the right reactor model and operating parameters, the contamination
5 with mixed plastics is beneficial to the PCI of the gas produced. For a second stage, comprising
6 a steam reforming process, the presence of water is beneficial for the production of fuel. In this
7 way, recurring problems in the pyrolysis of biomass and MSW, such as tar, water and plastic
8 mixtures becomes beneficial to the production of renewable biofuel based on the MSW
9 management model and the municipal solid waste treatment system designed for the
10 associations.

11 Considering the PNRS, an MSW management model was developed to mitigate the
12 socio-environmental impacts of urban solid waste and transform it into fuel and renewable
13 energy for waste collector associations. In line with each of the goals listed in this law, the
14 proposal of technological innovation for equipment that is more accessible to associations and
15 its provision in an organizational model of collaborative management for municipal MSW
16 management is presented as a solution to the barriers encountered by associations in processing
17 such waste , following directions for technological and organizational innovation parameterized
18 in the normative system of the PNRS, MROSC and MLI regulatory frameworks (AUTOR,
19 2023).

21 5.1. Socioeconomic and environmental benefits

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23 Considering that each 1kg of biomass produces 1.6 kg of CO₂, every month 7833 tons
24 of carbon dioxide will no longer be directly emitted and will return to circulation as an energy
25 product of a renewable nature and with high socioeconomic impact. Considering the

1 characterization of urban waste from garbage trucks by Carneiro (2007) and an estimate of 2%
2 by Rodrigues CJC et al (2023) of methane in the composition of the dry fraction of biomass,
3 corresponding carbon credits are generated corresponding to 43 tons per month of converted
4 methane.

5 In addition to the creation of new jobs, revenue of up to R\$854,891.00 per month is
6 expected from the operation with the sale of biochar in two associations, each with a RDF
7 treatment plant for synthesis and bottling of syngas, benefiting up to 110,769 low income
8 families.

9 It was found that the direct utilization of fuel generated by two-stage pyrolysis can
10 generate up to R\$56.165 mi in gross value at the end of the management model implementation
11 deadline (24 months), given by Silveira (2010). According to the dimensioning on the case-
12 study, the cost of each thermochemical reactor materials was estimated to be at least R\$230.327,
13 while the price for each of its gas bottling plants is estimated at up to R\$233,400. Given the
14 nature of the partnership-based management model and the complex tax dynamics involved,
15 the revenue distribution on the system may vary.

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17 **DECLARATION OF COMPETITION INTEREST**

18 The Authors report no conflicts of interest.

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25

1 **ATTACHMENTS**

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3 **Annex A – Table of goals for the national solid waste plan**

Goal Framework of the PNRS National Solid Waste Plan	
Goal 1. Increase the MSW management capacity of municipalities.	
Goal 2. Eliminate inappropriate final disposal practices and close controlled dumps and landfills	
Goal 3. Reduce the amount of waste and rejects sent for environmentally appropriate final disposal.	
Goal 4. Promote social inclusion and economic emancipation of collectors of reusable and recyclable materials	
Goal 5. Increase recycling of the dry fraction of MSW.	
Goal 6. Increase recycling of the organic fraction of MSW.	
Goal 7. Increase the recovery and energy use of MSW biogas.	
Goal 8. Increase energy recovery and use through thermal treatment of MSW.	
Source PNRS, Brazil (2010)	

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5 **Annex B: Table of equations used in sizing the CFB reactor**

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DESCRIPTION	EQUATION	COMMENTS
1- Heat required for pyrolysis:	$C = m_b \cdot c_{p,b} \cdot (T_\infty + T_0) + m_b \cdot \Delta H_r$	According to VELDEN et al. (2010) .
2- Overall heat transfer coefficients:	$q = m \cdot c \cdot (T_0 - T_i)$ $q = U_i \cdot A_i \cdot \Delta t_{lm}$ $h = \frac{11}{\left(U_i - \left(\frac{D_i}{2k} \right) \cdot \ln \left(\frac{D_e}{D_i} \right) - \frac{D_i}{(D_e \cdot h_e)} \right)}$	

3- Fourier's law of heat conduction	$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k_p}{\rho_p \cdot c_p} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right)$ $= D \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right)$ $D = \frac{k_p}{\rho_p \cdot c_p}$	
4- Biot number _	$Bi = r \cdot \frac{h}{k_p}$	
5- Energy balance in CFB	$\dot{m}_b \cdot h_b + \dot{m}_a \cdot h_a$ $= \dot{m}_g \cdot h_g + \dot{m}_{cin} \cdot h_{cin}$ $+ \dot{Q}_{ma}$	By Rodrigues CJC et al. (202 3)
6- General form of energy balance	$\frac{dE_{v.c}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{v.c} - \dot{W}_{v.c}$ $+ \sum \dot{m}_e \cdot \left(h_e + \frac{1}{2} \cdot V_e^2 + g \cdot Z_e \right)$ $+ \sum \dot{m}_s \cdot \left(h_s + \frac{1}{2} \cdot V_s^2 + g \cdot Z_s \right)$	By the First Law of Thermodynamics
7- Change in mass flow rate of species i (Mi)	$\frac{d}{dz} (M_i) = \sum_{j=1}^k v_{i,j} \cdot R_j(z), \text{ with } k=19;$	
8- Reaction rate for reaction j:	$R_j(z) = k_j \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_{ij}}{R \cdot T}\right) \cdot M_i$	
9- Continuity for gas phase	$\frac{d}{dz} (\epsilon g \cdot \rho g \cdot v g) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_j^k v_{i,j} \cdot R_j(z), \text{ with } N = 20$	

10- Relationship between mass flow and volume fraction	$\epsilon g . \rho g . v g = \sum_{i=1}^N M_i$	From MFIx Documentation Theory Guide (SYAMLAL, M., et al, 2003).
11- Continuity for biomass phase:	$\frac{d}{dz} (\epsilon b . \rho b . v b) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_j^k v_{i,j} . R_j(z)$	
12- Continuity for inert sand	$\frac{d}{dz} (\epsilon s . \rho s . v s) = 0$	Where $\epsilon s, \rho s, v s$ are the volume fraction, density (kg/m ³) and speed (m/s) of the sand.
13- Moment of the biomass phase	$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dz} (\epsilon b . \rho b . v b) &= -G(\epsilon b) . \frac{d\epsilon b}{dz} - \epsilon b . \frac{dp}{dz} \\ &+ \frac{d}{dz} \left(\epsilon b . \mu b . \frac{v b}{dz} \right) \\ &- \epsilon b . \rho b . g \\ &+ \beta . (v g - v b) \\ &- \frac{2 . f b . \epsilon b . \rho b . v b . v g}{D h} \end{aligned}$	
14- Energy balance for biomass phase	$\begin{aligned} \epsilon b . \rho b . v b . A c . c_{p,b} \frac{dT_b}{dz} \\ = -A_{s,bio} h_{bg} (T_b - T_g) \\ + \sum_j^k R_j . \Delta H_j \\ A_{s,bio} = \pi . d^2 . N b \end{aligned}$	
15- Energy balance for sand	$\begin{aligned} \epsilon s . \rho s . v s . A c . c_{p,s} \frac{dT_s}{dz} \\ = -A_{s,area} h_{s,g} (T_s - T_g) \\ A_{s,area} = \pi . d s^2 . N s \end{aligned}$	Heat transfer to the gas phase $A_{s,area} h_{s,g} (T_s - T_g)$ is

16- Gas phase energy equation	$\epsilon g \cdot \rho g \cdot v g \cdot A c \cdot c_{p,g} \frac{dT_g}{dz}$ $= A s \cdot a r e a \cdot h_{s g} \cdot (T_s - T_g)$ $+ A s, b i o \cdot h_{b, g} \cdot (T_b - T_g)$	
17- Heat transfer coefficient between solid and gaseous phase	$h_{s g} = \frac{6 \cdot k g \cdot \epsilon s \cdot N u s}{d p^2}$	N_{us} $= (7 - \epsilon g + 5 \cdot \epsilon g^5) \cdot (1 + 0,7 \cdot \Re_s^{0,2} \cdot P_r^{0,33})$ $+ (1,33 - 2,4 \cdot \epsilon g + 1,2 \cdot \epsilon g^2) \cdot \Re_s^{0,7} \cdot P_r^{0,33}$

Source: Adaptation by Marani I. and Silveira H. (2023);

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